

One Ceremony, Two Perspectives: Wedding and Music of a Diasporic Roma Community (2018)

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Abstract

My research investigate the cultural life of the Roma community, mainly from Kosovo but also from Montenegro and Macedonia; the study was conducted both in their countries of origin and among the diaspora in Italy, Switzerland, Germany, France and Sweden. Investigations have revolved around musical traditions as the main instruments for preserving, negotiating and redefining identity while participating in dialogue and intercultural exchange (Berengo Gardin and Staiti 1997; Staiti 2000, 2008 and 2016). The greater degree of porousness characterizing the borders between their countries of provenance and western Europe has granted Roma musicians more mobility and a new transnational culture circuit. In a short film, that is part of this paper, I documented a three-day event: the female part of a wedding party which took place in Dortmund. Musicians representing different musical traditions arrived in the city for the celebration: players from Kosovo, Macedonia and Bulgaria, but also from Serbia.

The Roma use video recordings as the objects of rituals and as a means for documenting the participation of families in wedding and circumcision feasts. The entire community cooperatively pays for these celebrations, covering not only the entire setting-up of the ceremony, but also video makers. The film that the Roma record during their celebrations, therefore, has the function of an oral and yet permanent record, not only of the community celebrations but also of the gifts, publicly recorded during the festival. In this ethnography centred on the transnationalism staged by this community, it seemed essential to me to seek to create dialogue between the filming strategies of those doing the observing and the strategies of those being observed.

*Una cerimonia, due prospettive: nozze e musica presso una comunità di rom in diaspora
La mia ricerca riguarda la vita culturale di una comunità di rom, soprattutto del Kosovo ma*

anche originari di Montenegro e Macedonia; l'indagine sul terreno è stata condotta sia nei loro luoghi di provenienza che in quelli della diaspora: Italia, Svizzera, Germania, Francia e Svezia. L'indagine si è focalizzata sulle tradizioni musicali come strumento principale per preservare, negoziare e ridefinire le proprie identità (Berengo Gardin e Staiti 1997; Staiti 2000, 2008 e 2016). L'ampio grado di porosità che oggi caratterizza i confini tra i loro luoghi di provenienza e l'Europa occidentale consente ai musicisti rom una mobilità maggiore che in passato, e offre loro nuove possibilità di circolazione transnazionale dei loro linguaggi musicali. In un breve film, che è parte di questo saggio, ho documentato la parte femminile di una festa nuziale, che ha avuto luogo nell'arco di tre giorni. Musicisti afferenti a diverse tradizioni sono arrivati in città per questo evento: cantori e suonatori provenienti da Kosovo, Macedonia e Bulgaria, ma anche dalla Serbia. I rom usano la registrazione video come oggetto dei riti e come strumento atto a documentare la partecipazione delle diverse famiglie alle feste di nozze e di circoncisione. L'intera comunità contribuisce a pagare questi eventi festivi, coprendo i costi non soltanto della cerimonia, ma anche delle riprese video. Il film che i rom girano e montano durante queste feste ha la funzione di documentazione orale, ma permanente, anche dell'ammontare dei contributi in denaro con cui ciascuna famiglia contribuisce, pubblicamente dichiarato e registrato nel corso dell'evento. In questo lavoro etnografico, centrato sul transnazionalismo messo in scena da questa comunità, mi è sembrato essenziale riflettere sulle strategie filmiche di chi osserva in relazione alle strategie filmiche di chi è osservato.

Film: *One Ceremony, Two Perspectives: Wedding and Music of a Diasporic Roma Community*, 12'15", 2018.

FIGURE 1. Screenshot from the film, showing a dance during the wedding party in Dortmund, Germany.

Anthropology and ethnomusicology studies have noted the fundamental role of music in contemporary processes of cultural change (Harrell-Bond, Voutira 1992; Martiniello, Lafleur 2008; White 2012; Agier 2016). From the 1980s onward, studies of diaspora

communities have discussed the role of music in specific communities and the relationship between past and present, tradition and innovation (Pettan 1992; Reyes 1999; Baily 1999; Staiti 2016; Silverman 2012, 2016, 2018), in relation to broader issues (globalization, trans-national networks, tourism flows: Kiwan, Meinhoff 2011; Krüger, Trandafoiu 2014), as part of consolidated migratory flows (Hemetek *et al.*, 2014), and among asylum seekers in refugee camps and contexts of conflict (Baily 1999; Broeske-Danielsen 2013).

Through music and ritual activities, migrants express, remember and reconstruct identities that are individual as well as collective, national or hybrid (Simonett 2001; Wong 2004); they imagine the culture they belong to and maintain their memory and awareness while establishing a place for themselves in the host society (Creet, Kitzman 2011; Lanette, Procopis 2016; Chávez 2017).

In Italy, migratory flows have been addressed through a “state of emergency” logic, with the result that policies, institutional practices and local and national agencies dealing with migrants (Dal Lago 2005; Maciotti, Pugliese 2003) have focused exclusively on jobs, the health system, education, and housing (Gomes 1998; Vitale 2009). The role played by the ritual and musical traditions of migrants in producing new forms of sociality and belonging, in a dynamic relation between cultures, has yet to receive adequate attention (Berengo Gardin, Staiti 1997).

The short film presented here is one of the outcomes of long-term research investigating the cultural life of the Roma community, mainly from Kosovo but also from Montenegro and, to a lesser extent, Macedonia; the study was conducted both in their countries of origin and among the diaspora in Italy, Switzerland, Germany, France and Sweden. The research mainly focused on the large community that has settled in Bologna (but has also maintained a presence in other Italian provinces, especially Brescia, Bolzano, Florence, Pescara, Lecce, Reggio Calabria, Messina, Catania and Palermo since the late 1980s: see, in particular, Berengo Gardin, Staiti 1997). This study has and continues to involve a detailed exploration of the modes of coexistence, places and practices of cohabitation, and informal processes through which the community engages as active subject in the construction of new forms of sociality. Specifically, investigations have revolved around musical traditions as the main instruments for preserving, negotiating and redefining identity while participating in dialogue and intercultural exchange (Berengo Gardin, Staiti 1997; Staiti 2000, 2008, 2016).

Rom people from Kosovo, Montenegro and Macedonia maintain in the societies in which they live and act, including as professional musicians, an identity that is at the same time strong and blurred, circumstantial, relational (Stewart 1997; Piasere 1991, 1995). Although they may be marginal on the social plane, they are central on the cultural one (Staiti 2008, 2016): they maintain and create connections among the traditions of different groups (for instance Albanian and Slavic speakers, Muslims and Christians), but are also the main agents of change (Staiti 2000; Pettan 1992). A relationship with extraneous cultures, including but not limited to musical ones, the assimilation

and innovative transformation of elements absorbed from the host context are all fundamental parts of their circumstantial and relational identity.

Roma from Kosovo arrived in Bologna in the 1990s as a consequence of the social and political tensions that led to the war in 1999. They lived in campers, cargo containers and shacks located in unauthorized camps as well as settlements run by the municipality. They begged, cleaned car windows at traffic lights and sold flowers in restaurants. Now they live in apartments in subsidized public housing, especially in the neighborhoods of Pilastro, Cirenaica, Barca and nearby municipalities, and work mostly in cleaning companies, with freight/shipping companies, as security guards in banks and shopping centers, and as waiters or bartenders. The social fabric of Pilastro – a suburb that was already populated by immigrants from other Italian provinces and foreign countries – in particular has been more fundamentally reshaped due to the many Roma living there. The overlapping of different ethnic groups in the Pilastro has produced conflicts and difficulties of communication, but the relational abilities of the residents, the social and educational policies implemented in the area, initiatives by schools, cooperatives, and cultural and sports associations have also given rise to a heightened degree of intercultural dialogue and integration.

The story of the Llukaci, a Roma family of musicians from the city of Gjakova in Kosovo, is at the centre of the story of Roma from Kosovo and Montenegro in Bologna. Lirije Llukaci (the wife of Baskim, a professional musician) was seriously injured during an attack perpetrated by the “band of the White One” in the settlement of Via Gobetti (December 23, 1990). On April 3, 2001, a fire broke out in a shack in the St. Caterina camp in Bologna (where the community had moved following the attack on via Gobetti). The flames claimed the lives of two children, Amanda and Alex Besic, aged 2 and 3 years old; the children of Suad Besic and Hana Llukaci, and Baskim Llukaci’s niece and nephew.¹ Following this incident, the municipality of Bologna dismantled the settlement in St. Caterina and all the families with the necessary requisites were assigned apartments in public housing complexes, most of which were located in the Pilastro neighborhood. The majority of the families had already been on waiting lists for these apartments for years, because almost all of the Roma from Kosovo living in Bologna had regular jobs and were fully documented in accordance with Italian immigration regulations. Some of them moved to other European countries, especially Germany. These included Remsija Llukaci, a well-known singer and keyboard player in the Roma diasporic community, the son of Baskim and Lirije and brother of Hana, Ribana Suzana, Oran, and Goran, all of whom remained in Bologna.

The Romani community ties were reinforced in a new and different way after the deaths of Amanda and Alex. They collectively planned and organized a public protest in the city center in which they asked for more organic and peaceful relations with local

¹ Regarding this event and its effects on my research methodology as well as the nature of my relationship with the communities of Roma from Kosovo and Montenegro in Bologna, see Staiti 2016: 142-169.

institutions and citizens, an opportunity for engagement and the chance to have their collective dignity restored. Nonetheless, these events triggered a process of re-organizing their internal and external relations and reflecting on their relational identity, a process that led to efforts to establish their own form of public representation and granted heightened attention to cultural dynamics.

These two events, the children's death and families' transferring to new housing, served to strengthen community ties beyond the usual relationships of kinship and alliance among families. The Roma from Kosovo and Montenegro living in Bologna built a cultural association, a youth soccer team and a women's dance troupe to help their children and grandchildren achieve integration in the city while preserving and transmitting their traditions. At the same time, they have started to reflect on the need to archive the audio and visual documents produced by their community and use these documents to build a history for themselves as Kosovar Roma, and Italians. Although I had already been carrying out documentation for over twenty years, this series of events caused them to develop new interest in my work: rather than condescension and friendly tolerance, they began to actually request my recording services, not only for use by private individuals and families but also for the community as a whole. The Roma themselves thus began to promote and encourage my research.

Young people who grew up in Bologna in conditions of hardship and marginalization are now part of the labor market, and some of them are also musicians with well-established positions in the community. Musical knowledge, which is widespread in the community and professionally cultivated by some of its members, is an important aspect of communication with other social groups: in Pilastro, the children of Roma musicians, grown and educated in Italy, have built close relationships with their Italian or migrant peers, turning refurbished basements and garages into places for musical production, engaging with old musical languages and developing new ones.

Some of these young people ask people such as myself, who conducted research with their parents, to resume studying their community, to combine past and present images and videos and to make the results of our investigations public.

The work carried out over the years on the musical traditions of the Roma, on the way they use these traditions both as a means of preserving identity and collective memory and as creative resources for redefining identity and engaging in intercultural exchange, negotiated in specific places and through concrete practices, becomes a useful tool for recounting their process of integration, the problems and tragedies that have fuelled it and the paths that have made it possible. Sebastian is a young man who spent his childhood living in a camper in the nomadic camp in the 1990s and begged on the street, attended a hotel management school and now works as a waiter in a restaurant in the city. When he asked me to go back to working with them, he told me that the Kosovar Roma are now a tolerably happy community and that it would make sense to publicly recount their process of integration, which took place by enhancing differences

rather than annulling them. Documenting their integration, he said, would be methodologically useful for evaluating and measuring the efficacy of the reception strategies put in place for other, more recent migratory flows.

Today, the greater degree of porousness characterizing the borders between their countries of provenance and Western Europe has granted Roma musicians more mobility and a new transnational culture circuit. The spread of low-cost airlines allows them to travel to their land of origin and other places in the diaspora where other members of their community have settled. As they live inside contexts dense with social relations, musicians maintain connections through social media; youngsters who grew up in Bologna can travel to play in their countries of origin or in other parts of Europe, enriching local traditions with musical and aesthetical elements that they developed in Italy. Conversely, musicians living in Kosovo, Macedonia and Bulgaria are hired for wedding or circumcision parties in Italy, Germany, Sweden and France. Local musical practices, the emblems of past hardships, cross ethnic, linguistic and national borders to become symbols of a pan-Roma and pan-Balkan identity that they proudly reclaim as their own.

Synthesizers and drums (or electronic pads) as well as, albeit less frequently, guitars and electric basses, have long been a permanent part of the traditional instrumental ensembles. The most commonly used wind instruments are the alto saxophone in E flat and the clarinet: in B flat in the Albanian culture area and in G for musicians from western Macedonia and Bulgaria, areas more closely linked to the Turkish tradition. The new generation of instrumentalists has achieved remarkable levels of virtuosity, perhaps more than previous generations. They have more opportunities for training thanks to their more frequent and easy opportunities for meeting up, which promote exchange and learning, low-cost access to equipment for recording and sound processing as well as the use of social media. Young musicians can record and listen to themselves again and again, they can also listen to the performances of masters from the previous generation and their colleagues or recordings by virtuoso players from other traditions, at real or reduced tempos, in order to learn and master techniques, languages, melodic structures and improvisational formulas.

Up to a few years ago, Roma from areas in which Albanian is the dominant language (Kosovo, part of Montenegro and Macedonia) defined themselves outside of their own community as Albanians and publicly spoke Albanian, because they considered it to be more socially acceptable. The music played at their parties was the same that was performed throughout that area of the Balkans, even at the weddings of non-Roma Albanians who hired professional gypsies for their celebrations (Staiti 2016: 80-89).² Certainly, a Serbian brass band would never perform at a wedding party of Muslim Albanians: not only because their musical and choreographic traditions are different, but also and especially because that music was considered to symbolize a different and enemy culture. As the documentary shows, however, the Albanian-speaking Kosovar Roma who grew up in Bologna

² On the use of the term “Gypsy” instead of “Roma”, see Staiti 2019: 191-192.

and moved to Germany now proudly feature the participation of a Serbian Roma band, from Vranje, at their own feasts, because they no longer believe that their group identity is mainly Albanian; they also feel that they are Roma and pan-European. In such a context, in short, the Roma do not bow to religious, political and linguistic divisions, and these divisions are partially giving way to a new transnational Roma identity.

The Balkan Roma, diasporic populations or segments of populations who escaped crises and wars, currently populate the whole of Western Europe. In the neighbourhoods of every European city and, most extensively, on social media, they interact effectively with other immigrants and with resident populations. The Balkan Roma living in Italy have been educated in Italy, and they speak and write in fluent Italian. Those living in France speak and write French, those in Germany or Austria speak German, those in Great Britain speak English, those in Spain speak Spanish, those in Sweden speak Swedish. They understand the languages spoken by their relatives living in other European countries; they are also fluent speakers of at least Serbian or Albanian, often both, and many of them also speak Turkish and some Bulgarian or Macedonian dialects. In addition, they share the Romani language, a lingua franca which, although broken down into various dialects, allows them to communicate with people from different areas. In recent years, the use of online communication channels has led to the emergence of a written version of this language that used to be used only orally, by native speakers (and transcribed only by linguists, dialectologists, historians and members of a few, unrepresentative cultural or political associations). In this context, Facebook may very well serve the function for Roma people that Pietro Bembo's *Prose nelle quali si ragiona della volgar lingua* served for the establishment of Italian.³ This language functions to bridge distances, cross borders and continents, preserve and cultivate its (linguistic, musical, culinary) traditions and adapt and reconnect them to new and unfamiliar contexts. It does so, for example, by exchanging cooking recipes, commenting on sporting events, circulating the news of a wedding party or a meeting among friends, communicating with family branches, friends and acquaintances living far away. Alongside messages in Romani, they write others in Albanian or Serbian, Italian, French, German or Swedish: through these other languages, they circumscribe small portions of their community, but they also share things with friends, acquaintances and, by now, Italian, French, German, Swedish, Albanian, Serbian, Macedonian, Bulgarian or Romanian relatives as well. Not to mention Arab, Turkish, Moldavian, Ghanaian and Peruvian neighbour and friends.

This is a short film documenting a specific three-day event: the female part of Remsija Llukaci's daughter's wedding party which took place in Dortmund.⁴ Relatives from all over Europe and musicians representing different musical traditions arrived in the city for the celebration: players from Kosovo, Macedonia and Bulgaria, but also from Serbia.

³ About the use of Romani in virtual spaces by a diasporised community originating from Mitrovica, Kosovo see Leggio 2015.

⁴ The Llukaci family invited me to the event; I left from Bologna with the sister, the brother in law,

Some came from their countries of origin, others live in different countries throughout Western Europe. A rapper also participated.

Today, we ethnologists tend to attribute great and often excessive importance to the innovative features of traditions, at the expense of practices of conservation and perpetuation. Without realizing that, in many ways, the videos people share on YouTube or elsewhere, for example, include more elements of continuity with the traditions of village communities than elements of adaptation to the globalized world.

The Roma use video recordings with special intensity as the objects of rituals and, at least as importantly, as a means for documenting the participation of families in wedding and circumcision feasts (Staiti 2016). The entire community cooperatively pays for these celebrations, covering not only the entire setting-up of the ceremony, the musicians and the food served to participants but also video makers using expensive, professional-grade equipment. The cash contribution that feast participants pay is supposed to be equal to the amount they received when their families were the ones to organize a feast; the host, if is hosted in the future by the family of one of the participants, will in turn pay as a gift a sum of money not less than the one he himself received. The film that the Roma record during their celebrations, therefore, has the function of an oral and yet permanent record, not only of the community celebrations but also of these payments, publicly recorded into the microphone during the festival. In this brief visual ethnography centred on the transnationalism staged by this community during the Llukaci family's wedding feast, it thus seemed essential to me to seek to create dialogue between the filming strategies of those doing the observing and the strategies of those being observed as well as the game of mirrors that follows, a dialogue which is also a chance to reflect on my purposes and techniques of dissemination.

Script of the film

On March 23, 2018, several Roma families from Kosovo, Montenegro, and Macedonia met in Dortmund, Germany, for the wedding party of a famous singer's daughter.

Many musicians from different traditions met to offer a musical homage to their colleague.

Both the diaspora and a new sense of a shared Roma and pan-balkan identity gathered, in the same venue, musicians from varied traditions.

Azat King, a Turkish clarinet player from Macedonia and Naser Gilani, a saxophone player from Gilan (Kosovo).

The bride's procession was accompanied by a Roma brass band from Vranje, in Serbia.

Remsija's nephew and, in Dortmund, they hosted me. The video documentation and this publication are the product of a subtle negotiation that I further examined in the film. On the subject of the marriage rituals in Kosovo as well as for a focus on the moments dedicated to women, see Staiti 2016.

Several musicians and singers performed: among them Sultan Haioli, Ernim Ibrahimimi, Haki Bulgaria, Cita,

The weeping and henna ceremony was accompanied by Uka Gashi (“Uk’ Jakova”), singer and tambourine player from Gjakova (Kosovo).

There was even a rapper: Amanat Ali Khan (Denorecords).

Thus the musical diaspora reshaped the ritual set into a new transnational dimension.

The party took place in a banquet hall run by a family of Roma from Kosovo.

“Studio Bejta”, a company of Roma from Kosovo who have immigrated to Germany, provided the video services.

At the end of the party the entire video of the event was given to the participants: 4 DVDs, for a total duration of 7 hours: from 7.15pm on the 23rd to 2.45pm on March 24th.

They used 3 video-cams: one on a crane 5 meters long, one on a tripod, one hand-held, with motorized stabilizer.

Video mixing was shown live on a large screen.

We used 3 small handy-cams, two hand-held and one on an tripod. Obviously, so as not to be invasive and indiscreet.

One can find out the differences between their shootings and ours’.

They preferred a large framing, and often overlap two or three screens.

Roma use video as a ritual tool, literally in a documentary way: the video has to record who was there, who did what and when.

This because every ceremony shows and rebuilds their social structure.

People must be filmed using full body shots; ritual time is never manipulated or compressed.

Lirije, the bride’s grandmother, suggested we shouldn’t publish our material on YouTube.

Knowing that that would never happen.

The next day Hana, her daughter, sent me WhatsApp messages with the links to the full video of the party, obviously published on YouTube by her brother.

Lirije’s request only mirrors the ceremony’s liturgy and the liturgy of our relationship. And above all the liturgy of the ties that they establish in their family, their community and the outside world.

Even if the recordings had been identical, what was important wasn’t WHERE they were published, but WHO published them and why.

Our network of contacts only partially overlap.

Today, every reflection on method and style in visual ethnomusicology must take into account both the diverse film languages, perspectives and functions pursued by the actors and the researcher.

This short film was realized with the collaboration and agreement of the Llukaci family. However I never asked them to sign a consent form: as it would un-necessarily

influence that deep, yet subtle web of what is both implicit and explicit; the foundation of every serious and responsible relationship between the observed and the observer.

Shooting: Studio Bejta, Jing Ru Dong, Nico Staiti.

Audio: Studio Bejta, Nico Staiti.

Editing: Jing Ru Dong

English translation: Rhodri Jones

Catering service: Hana Llukaci

Managerial services: Remsija Llukaci

Author: Nico Staiti

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